

HRJust Intersect Observatory’s Mission: Notes on the Methodological Framework

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HRJust Intersect Observatory Mission:

Notes on the Methodological Framework

The Intersect Observatory (<https://hrjust-intersect-observatory.eu/>) is created as part of the HRJust project.

The Intersect Observatory is the first one of its kind to include materials on human rights justifications in the field of climate, COVID and migration through gender and intersectionality perspective.

The Observatory role is to monitor human rights justification through the findings and materials produced by the HRJust project and its aim is to raise knowledge and promote a healthy debate and dialogue in this area through its digital library, work-in-progress seminars, web interviews and much more.

The concept of an observatory for examining and monitoring trends in a research area comes from analogy with the facilities of astronomy and the idea that close and consistent observation is essential to understand and follow the development of a given topic. The Observatory method in humanities serves indeed “as a utility, or multi-purpose vehicle, for describing and responding to emerging community issues quickly and gathering data and qualitative findings as required”.¹ An Observatory is thus a “Living Lab”.²

In this respect, the Intersect Observatory offers a space where users and stakeholders (academia, policy officers, civil society) can find materials developed by the other WPs of the project.

In particular, the materials offered by the Observatory will help answering the following overarching questions in the project, moving from the relevant theoretical framework to the empirical level:

How do States defend and legitimise its actions through human rights?

Compare the general and the particular.

What role does geopolitics play in strategy, resources and reach.

What role has EU in comparison between internal to EU and external to EU?

The following materials are helpful in tackling the above-mentioned issues.³

¹ Guidotti T. L. (2022). The observatory: a model for studies in health, society, and the environment. *Journal of environmental studies and sciences*, 12(4), 827–837. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13412-022-00786-6>.

² World Bank (2016). The social observatory: a living lab for developing a science of delivery. 28 January 2016. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2016/01/28/the-social-observatory-a-living-lab-for-developing-a-science-of-delivery>.

³ The following table will be regularly updated throughout the project lifetime, when WPs will keep contributing to it.

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Overarching questions	Materials
<i>How do States defend and legitimise its actions through human rights?</i>	<p>Reading lists, working papers and video series in the Intersect Library and in the Gender & Intersectionality section</p> <p>Discussion through events and webinar – with the participation of the relevant stakeholders</p> <p>Direct access from the users of the website to experts (i.e. Consortium members)´ opinions and comments through the Contact our Expert form in the Intersect Library and in the Gender & Intersectionality section</p>
<i>Compare the general and the particular.</i>	<p>Reading lists, working papers and video series in the Intersect Library and in the Gender & Intersectionality section</p> <p>Discussion through events and webinar – with the participation of the relevant stakeholders</p> <p>Direct access from the users of the website to experts (i.e. Consortium members)´ opinions and comments through the Contact our Expert form in the Intersect Library and in the Gender & Intersectionality section</p>
<i>What role does geopolitics play in strategy, resources and reach.</i>	<p>Reading lists, working papers and video series in the Intersect Library and in the Gender & Intersectionality section</p> <p>Discussion through events and webinar – with the participation of the relevant stakeholders</p> <p>Direct access from the users of the website to experts (i.e. Consortium members)´ opinions and comments through the Contact our Expert form in the Intersect Library and in the Gender & Intersectionality section</p>
<i>What role has EU in comparison between internal to EU and external to EU?</i>	<p>Reading lists, working papers and video series in the Intersect Library and in the Gender & Intersectionality section</p> <p>Discussion through events and webinar – with the participation of the relevant stakeholders</p> <p>Direct access from the users of the website to experts (i.e. Consortium members)´ opinions and comments through the Contact our Expert form in the Intersect Library and in the Gender & Intersectionality section</p>

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